

Crystal structure of N,N'-bis-thiophene-2-yl-methylene-propane-1,3-diamine

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Abstract : The title compound, N,N'-bis-thiophene-2-yl-methylene-propane-1,3-diamine (**1**), C₁₃H₁₄N₂S₂ was synthesized in dry methanol. On crystallization from the methanolic mother liquor, single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction of **1** were harvested. The compound crystallizes in the monoclinic crystal system with P_{2(1)/c} space group having $a = 8.4379(2)$, $b = 16.5735(4)$, $c = 10.6494(3)$ Å, $\beta = 115.703(2)$, $V = 1341.91(6)$ Å³ and $Z = 4$. This compound is a potential bidentate ligand with two nitrogens only as donor centres as evidenced from all the crystal structures hitherto reported on this type of systems.

Keywords : Schiff base, bidentate ligand, X-ray crystal structure.

Introduction

The term "Schiff base" was coined after Hugo Schiff¹. Bidentate Schiff base ligand, N,N'-bis-thiophene-2-yl-methylene-propane-1,3-diamine (**1**), had been reported as early as in 2001². It had been shown that **1** may act as a potential PVC membrane electrode that can be coated directly on graphite. This modified electrode selectively manifests a Nernstian response for Cu²⁺ over a wide variety of other metal ions in a broad concentration window³. Even the authors had employed this ligand for the determination of ultra-trace amount of lead, cadmium and copper ions in environmental and biological samples⁴. Curiously, the crystal structure of this ligand is hitherto unknown. However, it has been proposed that this potential ligand acts as a tetradentate ligand with two nitrogen donor centers and two sul-

phur donor centers. Karthikeyan *et al.* reported a Ru^{III} complex stabilised out of this ligand⁵. But the crystal structure of this ruthenium complex has not been reported. Only the crystal structure of a Pd^{II} complex of this titled ligand is known in the literature⁶. The sulphur centers are found to be non-coordinating in this structure. Of late, similar types of thiophene based Schiff base ligands have been reported by Patra *et al.*⁷. There also the sulphur atoms are found to be non-coordinating. Recently we have reported a trinuclear copper(II) complex of a thiophene based Schiff base ligand. The X-ray crystal structure of this trinuclear copper(II) system reveals that the sulphur atoms are non-coordinating too⁸. Even to shed light on the binding propensities of this class of ligands employing thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde as a moiety, a good number of transition metal complexes

have been synthesized and characterized without any crystal structure⁹. Herein we wish to report the crystal structure of this titled ligand. It is a point to note that **1** bears immense significance from analytical viewpoint.

Experimental

All chemicals were of analytical reagent grade. 1,3-Diaminopropane and thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and were used as received without further purification.

Physical measurements :

An electro-thermal digital melting point apparatus (SUMSIM India) was used to determine the melting point of **1** and is uncorrected. C, H and N microanalyses were performed by a Perkin-Elmer 2400II elemental analyser. A Shimadzu FTIR-8400S spectrophotometer was used to record the FT-IR spectra (KBr disc) of the ligand in the range 400–4000 cm^{-1} . 300 MHz ^1H NMR spectrum of **1** was recorded (in CDCl_3 : reference, TMS) on a Bruker DPX300 spectrometer. ESI mass spectral data (in methanol) in the positive ionization mode was acquired on a Waters Q-tof Micro YA263 spectrometer.

Single crystals of **1**, suitable for X-ray crystallographic analysis, were selected following examination under a microscope. Intensity data were collected at 293(2) K for **1** on a Bruker Smart Apex II diffractometer equipped with a 1K CCD instrument by using a graphite monochromated MoK_α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Cell parameters were determined using SMART software¹⁰. Data reduction and corrections were performed using SAINTPlus¹⁰. Absorption corrections were made via SADBAS¹¹. The structure was solved by direct methods with the program SHELXS-97 and was refined by full-matrix least-squares methods on all F^2 data with SHELXL-97¹². All structural refinement data of **1** are given in Table 1. Some selected bond lengths and bond angles are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for **1**

CCDC No.	1541714
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$
Formula weight	262.38
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Wavelength (\AA)	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$\text{P}_{2(1)/c}$
Unit cell dimensions :	
a (\AA)	8.4379(2)
b (\AA)	16.5735(4)
c (\AA)	10.6494(3)
α ($^\circ$)	90
β ($^\circ$)	115.703(2)
γ ($^\circ$)	90
Volume (\AA^3)	1341.91(6)
Z	4
ρ_{calcd} (g/cm^3)	1.299
Absorption coefficient (mm^{-1})	0.376
$F(000)$	552
Crystal size (mm)	$0.21 \times 0.12 \times 0.25$
θ range for data collection (deg)	2.45 to 27.07
Limiting indices	$-10 \leq h \leq 10, -21 \leq k \leq 21, -12 \leq l \leq 13$
Reflections collected/unique	21919/2930 ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0248$)
Completeness of theta = 27.07	99.5%
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	2930/0/154
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.067
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0333, wR_2 = 0.0885$
R indices (all data)	$R_1 = 0.0402, wR_2 = 0.0935$
Largest diff. Peak and hole	0.174 and $-0.242 \text{ e. \AA}^{-3}$

Table 2. Selected bond distances (\AA) and angles ($^\circ$) for **1**

S1-C1	1.7030(18)	S1-C4	1.7182(15)
S2-C4	1.712(2)	S2-C10	1.7125(14)
N1-C5	1.265(2)	N1-C6	1.4575(19)
C1-S1-C4	91.63(8)	C13-S2-C10	91.40(9)
C5-N1-C6	117.46(14)	C9-N2-C8	116.38(14)
C2-C1-S1	112.37(14)	C2-C1-H1	123.8
C11-C10-C9	126.57(14)	C11-C10-S2	110.47(11)
C9-C10-S2	122.96(11)	C10-C11-C12	113.32(16)

Synthesis and crystallization :

Preparation of N,N'-bis-thiophene-2-yl-methylene-propane-1,3-diamine (1) :

0.16 mL (2 mmol) of 1,3-diaminopropane was taken in a round bottom flask and was thoroughly dissolved in 20 mL of dry methanol. To this solution, 0.36 mL (4 mmol) of thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde was added dropwise to obtain a yellow solution (Scheme 1). The resulting reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 4 h. After refluxing, the intense yellow solution so derived was kept in a refrigerator for slow evaporation. After 7 days of standing, when the volume of the solution reduced nearly to 2 mL, the separated yellow mass was filtered and washed with ice-cold diethyl ether. Then it was vacuum dried over fused CaCl₂. Yield : 259 mg (49%). m.p. : 42–45°C. C₁₃H₁₄N₂S₂ : (262.112), Anal. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₄N₂S₂ : C, 59.52; H, 5.38; N, 10.68. Found : C, 59.64; H, 5.31; N, 10.71%; FT-IR (KBr) : ν /cm⁻¹ : 1603 (C=N of imine), 1458s (C=C ring vibration), 763s (four adjacent C-H bonds on the ring);

Scheme 1. Synthetic scheme of TPDA (1).

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ /ppm 2.10 (2H, q, -CH₂- protons), 3.68 (4H, t, -CH₂- protons), 7.08 (2H, d, thiophene ring protons), 7.29 (2H, d, thiophene ring protons), 7.39 (2H, d, thiophene ring protons) and 8.40 (2H, s, -CH=N proton); UV-Vis (MeOH) : λ_{max} (ϵ /M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) 303 nm (18,871), 308 nm (18,060); ESI-MS (positive ion mode in CH₃OH) (*m/z*) : 263.04 (Calcd. 263.11) for [1+H]⁺ (100%) and 285.02 (Calcd. 285.11) for [1+Na]⁺ (20%). The ¹H NMR and ESI mass spectra of **1** are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

Shining yellow single crystals, suitable for X-ray crystallography, were grown by slow evaporation of a moderately concentrated methanolic solution of the compound in a refrigerator in the course of its purification.

Crystal structure of N,N'-bis-thiophene-2-yl-methylene-propane-1,3-diamine (TPDA) :

The compound TPDA is a di-condensate product of 1,3-diaminopropane and thiophene-2-carboxaldehyde. The ORTEP diagram is shown in Fig. 3. The newly formed C=N bond distances are 1.265(2) and 1.258(2) Å for N1-C5 and N2-C9 bonds respectively. Those bond distances are shorter than the C-N bond distance of 1,3-diaminopropane moiety, 1.4575(19) and 1.457(2) Å respectively for N1-C6 and N2-C8. The mean deviation of the least-square planes for the two thiophene rings S1/C1/C2/C3/C4 and S2/C10/C11/C12/C13 are 0.0001 and 0.0024 Å

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of **1** in CDCl₃.

Fig. 2. ESI mass spectrum of **1** in methanol.

Fig. 3. ORTEP of **1** with 50% probability.

Table 3. Hydrogen-bond geometry (Å, °) for **1**

D-H...A	d(D-H)	d(H...A)	d(D...A)	∠D-H...A
C3-H3...N1 ⁱ	0.93	2.59	3.495 (2)	164.1
C7-H7A...S1 ⁱⁱ	0.97	3.00	3.915(2)	158.7

Symmetry code : i x, -y+3/2, z+1/2; ii x-1, -y+3/2, z-1/2

respectively. This indicates that each 5-membered ring system is essentially coplanar. The dihedral angle between the two planes is 56.74(5)°. All the bond distances and bond angles are within their stipulated ranges. There are some weak interactions in the structure (Fig. 4 and Table 3). The distances of C7...S1ⁱ and C3...N1ⁱⁱ are 3.915(2) and 3.495(2) Å (Symmetrical codes : i x-1, -y+3/2, z-1/2; ii x, -y+3/2, z+1/2), respectively.

Fig. 4. X-Ray packing diagram of **1**.

Conclusions

Here, we have synthesized and characterized a Schiff base (TPDA). The crystal structure of this ligand has also been determined for the first time. It is a point to note that this is an analytical reagent of sufficient contemporary analytical importance. This has been employed for the determination of ultra-trace amount of lead, cadmium and copper ions in environmental and biological samples. However, no crystal structure of any metal compound of this ligand is known except for a palladium complex. Thus, the crystal structure as described here even for the bare ligand may shed light on the coordination perspectives of this reagent.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

The cif file of **1** was deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC No. 1541714). This data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from

the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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